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Humidity response of optical fibres with hygroscopic coatings and its temperature dependence

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E-mail: xin.lu@bam.de**Keywords:** humidity sensor, optical fibre sensors, optical frequency domain reflectometer, Rayleigh scattering

Abstract

Optical fibres with hygroscopic coatings are widely used in structural health monitoring to acquire the humidity information. Water absorption-induced coating expansion leads to a strain change in the silica fibre, which can be measured by point and distributed strain fibre sensors and used to quantify the environmental humidity. In this paper, the strain transfer from the coating to the fibre is described by both 1D and 3D models. The impact of the coating property on the humidity induced strain is theoretically analysed. Since the properties of the sensing fibre are temperature-dependent, the humidity response obtained by the strain-based approach may change under different thermal conditions. The humidity response of fibres with different polyimide coatings is characterized by a commercial optical frequency domain reflectometer under different temperature conditions. The experimental results confirm the temperature dependence of the humidity response as the sensitivity of all the tested fibres decreases as the temperature increases.

1. Introduction

Humidity is an important parameter in structural health monitoring. A proper humidity level should be maintained; otherwise metal corrosion can occur when the environment is too humid, and concrete may crack if the condition is very dry. Both situations may cause hazardous consequences to the structural integrity. Therefore, humidity should be monitored throughout the structure around the clock, and a long sensing distance is usually required considering the size of large infrastructures such as tunnels and bridges. The humidity sensors based on optical fibre stand out in this case due to the intrinsic advantages of the fibre, like ultra-low loss, small size, and lightweight, immunity to electromagnetic interference [1, 2].

So far, different types of fibre-based humidity sensors have been proposed for structure health monitoring. The most primitive fibre humidity sensor is essentially a water detector based on a swellable polymer surrounding the fibre. The polymer absorbs water and expands in volume, so an extra bending loss is introduced to the fibre and the water information is acquired from the optical power variation [3]. Later, strain-based methods have been proposed which relies on a hygroscopic fibre coating, such as polyimide and polyetherimide [4–8]. The water absorption induced coating volume change leads to the expansion or compression of the fibre, so the humidity information can be retrieved from the strain [4]. There also exist other types of fibre-based sensors to quantify the relative humidity (RH). Most polymer optical fibres (POFs) demonstrate water affinity and the water absorbed in the fibre core can induce extra fibre loss [9–11]. Recently, various novel types of fibre optic humidity sensors, such as graphene oxide coated long period grating, gelatin coated singlemode-multimode fibre structure, side-polished fibre coupler, polyvinylidene fluoride Fabry–Perot cavity, and integrated Mach–Zehnder Interferometer have been proposed and demonstrated good performance [12–16]. The humidity response of different fibre sensors has also been investigated [17–19].

The POFs seem to be a good candidate for humidity sensing because environmental variations usually manifest as changes in optical power [11]. However, the POF has higher attenuation and its working temperature is limited to ~ 100 °C, meaning that POF based sensors are restricted to a specific sensing

distance and temperature range. Therefore, the strain-based measurement is of particular interest among all the aforementioned methods because it requires only standard silica fibres, whereas the other sensors operate in either special fibres or complex fibre structures. In addition, fibre strain sensing is a mature technique. It can be performed in discrete point or spatially resolved way, and there are many commercially available products. The strain-based fibre optic humidity sensor is thus expected to be widely used in the future and its performance is highly dependent on the sensing fibre. It is of great importance to understand the strain transfer from the coating to the fibre and the influence of the coating properties. Furthermore, the humidity response needs to be characterized under different conditions considering the practical applications.

Although the fibre optic humidity sensors based on the strain measurement have demonstrated excellent performance in the lab, their practical applications usually suffer from ambient temperature variation. For example, with most fibre sensors discriminating temperature and strain is difficult [20], such that a small temperature variation can be mistakenly considered as a change in humidity, causing a measurement error. Moreover, some physical and mechanical properties of the hygroscopic coating are temperature dependent [21]. Under various thermal conditions, the same humidity change can consequently induce different strain variations in the fibre, impairing the accuracy of the humidity measurement.

In this paper, the mechanical interaction between the coating and the silica fibre is analysed using 1D and 3D models. The 1D model focuses on the shape change in the longitudinal direction, whereas the 3D model based on Lamé's equations, takes the deformation in radial direction into consideration [22], so it estimates a larger strain than the 1D model. The impact of the coating properties on the induced strain, e.g. the coefficient of humidity expansion (CHE), thickness, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, is theoretically analysed. The humidity sensitivity of optical fibres with different polyimide coatings is characterized by a commercial optical frequency domain reflectometer (OFDR) under different temperature conditions. Most importantly, the results demonstrate the humidity response is temperature dependent as the characterized humidity sensitivity decreases at a higher temperature. This temperature-dependence makes sensor calibration at different temperature conditions necessary to guarantee the reliability of the fibre optic humidity sensor.

2. Theoretical analysis of the strain transfer

2.1. 1D model

The simplest sensing fibre for the humidity measurement consists of only two parts: silica fibre and hygroscopic coating. The former is used as a sensing and transmission medium for the light and the latter as a transducer to convert the humidity into a parameter the fibre can measure, which is strain in this case. The configuration of such a fibre is depicted in figure 1. The cross-section of this fibre is shown in figure 1(a), the dotted area is the reactive coating and the grey part represents the silica fibre. Although the hygroscopic coating absorbs water and swells in all directions, the 1D model considers just the expansion in the longitudinal direction that evidently has significant influence on the induced strain in the fibre, as shown in figure 1(b).

The water intake by the glass fibre and the coating leads to the longitudinal strain, which can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_f = \alpha_f \Delta RH + \sigma_f / E_f \\ \varepsilon_c = \alpha_c \Delta RH + \sigma_c / E_c \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where ΔRH is the RH change, ε_f is the generated strain, α is the CHE, σ represents the stress, E represents Young's modulus and the subscripts f and c represent the glass fibre and the hygroscopic coating, respectively. In this case, the fibre and the coating are assumed to be rigidly connected with each other at the fibre ends, e.g. $\varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_c$. Hence,

$$\alpha_f \Delta RH + \sigma_f / E_f = \alpha_c \Delta RH + \sigma_c / E_c. \quad (2)$$

Since the whole fibre is free from external forces, a boundary condition exists as [4]

$$A_f \sigma_f + A_c \sigma_c = 0. \quad (3)$$

where A_f and A_c are the cross-section areas for the silica fibre and the coating, respectively. Thus $A_f = \pi r_f^2$ and $A_c = \pi (r_c^2 - r_f^2)$, where r_f and r_c represent the radii of fibre cladding and fibre coating, respectively. And r_c is equal to the cladding radius plus the coating thickness. Based on equations (2) and (3), the fibre stress σ_f can be obtained. Assuming the optical fibre and hygroscopic coating are isotropic and demonstrate linear

elasticity for the analysis on the humidity induced strain [4], the strain in the fibre can then be obtained based on Hooke's law as:

$$\varepsilon_f = \sigma_f/E_f = (\alpha_c - \alpha_f)A_cE_c/(A_fE_f + A_cE_c) \cdot \Delta\text{RH}. \quad (4)$$

This analysis has been widely used [4–6].

2.2. 3D model

As presented above, the 1D model takes only the longitudinal expansion into consideration. As a matter of fact, the coating expands in all directions due to the water absorption. And the related stresses change in radial, tangential, longitudinal dimensions can be described by Lamé's equations as [22]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_i^R \\ \sigma_i^\theta \\ \sigma_i^z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_i + 2\mu_i & \xi_i & \xi_i \\ \xi_i & \xi_i + 2\mu_i & \xi_i \\ \xi_i & \xi_i & \xi_i + 2\mu_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_i^R - \alpha_i\Delta\text{RH} \\ \varepsilon_i^\theta - \alpha_i\Delta\text{RH} \\ \varepsilon_i^z - \alpha_i\Delta\text{RH} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where R , θ , and z represent the radial, tangential, longitudinal dimensions respectively, i can be f and c for the glass fibre and the coating, and μ_i are the Lamé parameters, written as

$$\begin{cases} \xi_i = \eta_i E_i / [(1 + \eta_i)(1 - 2\eta_i)] \\ \mu_i = E_i / [2(1 + \eta_i)] \end{cases}. \quad (6)$$

Respectively, and η_i denotes the corresponding Poisson's ratio. The factor ε_i^R , ε_i^θ , and ε_i^z in Lamé's equations represent the corresponding strains in radial, tangential, longitudinal directions, expressed as [22, 23]

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_i^R = U_i + V_i/r^2 \\ \varepsilon_i^\theta = U_i - V_i/r^2 \\ \varepsilon_i^z = W_i \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where r represents the distance from the analysed position to the fibre centre, U_i , V_i and W_i are constants that can be determined by the boundary conditions.

Firstly, the humidity induced strain in radial and tangential directions (ε_f^r and ε_f^θ) must be finite at the fibre centre $r = 0$, so $V_f = 0$. Secondly, to ensure the continuity between the fibre and the coating, the following relations must be hold:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_f^R(r_f) = \sigma_c^R(r_f) \\ U_f r_f = U_c r_f - V_c / r_f \end{cases}. \quad (8)$$

The radius of the sensing fibre is very small compared with the fibre length, thus the coated fibre can be considered as an ultra-long and thin cylinder, so

$$\varepsilon_f^z = \varepsilon_c^z = \varepsilon_f. \quad (9)$$

Due to the plain strain approximation [23].

Finally, the following two boundary conditions must hold:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_c^R(r_c) = 0 \\ \sigma_c^z(r_c) \cdot A_c + \sigma_f^z(r_f) \cdot A_f = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Because the fibre is subject to no external force [23].

The constants U_i , V_i and W_i can be inserted into the boundary conditions as presented by equations (6)–(10) and analytically solved. As a result, the humidity induced strain in the fibre ε_f can be expressed in a similar form as equation (4)

$$\varepsilon_f = \left(\frac{\alpha_c E_c A_c C_c + \alpha_f E_f A_f C_f}{+ E_c E_f A_c C_{cf}} \right) / \left(\frac{E_c A_c C_c + E_f A_f C_f}{+ E_c E_f A_c D_{cf}} \right) \cdot \Delta RH. \quad (11)$$

The coefficients C_c , C_f , C_{cf} and D_{cf} are expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} C_f = E_f [(1 - \eta_c - 2\eta_c^2) A_c + (1 + \eta_c) \pi r_c^2] \\ C_c = E_c A_c (1 - \eta_f - 2\eta_f^2) \\ C_{cf} = \alpha_c A_{\text{sum}} (1 + \eta_c) + A_f \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_f (1 + \eta_f - 2\eta_c - 2\eta_f \eta_c) \\ -2\alpha_c \eta_f (1 + \eta_c) \end{bmatrix} \\ D_{cf} = (1 + \eta_c) A_c + (3 - 4\eta_f \eta_c - \eta_f) A_f \end{cases}, \quad (12)$$

where $A_{\text{sum}} = \pi (r_c^2 + r_f^2)$.

Compared with the result of 1D model as shown by equation (4), the expression of the humidity induced strain obtained by the 3D model is notably more complex. An extra term exists in both the numerator and denominator, which is related to the product of the Young's moduli of fibre and the coating. These terms describe the interaction of the two sections during the expansion or shrinkage process. This comprehensive study takes the Poisson's ratio into consideration, distinguishing it from the previous analysis focusing on the 1D model. It is worth noting that the humidity-induced strain can be analysed for arbitrary coating layers based on Lamé's equations. However, the analytical solution of the strain becomes too complex to express in the multi-layer case.

2.3. Comparison of the 1D and 3D models

The analysis above shows that different models lead to different induced strains, and the generated strain is highly dependent on the physical parameters of the optical fibre and the hygroscopic material, such as their sizes, Young's moduli and coefficients of humidity expansion. The properties of the standard silica fibre are well known and fixed. In this paper, the radius, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the fibre are taken as $62.5 \mu\text{m}$, 72 GPa and 0.17 , respectively [23]. Furthermore, the CHE of the optical fibre α_f is assumed to be negligible [6]. On the other hand, the hygroscopic coating can be designed to achieve various humidity responses. According to the analysis above, the induced strain depends on the properties of the hygroscopic coating, i.e. thickness, CHE, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio. Since the last parameter is not considered in the 1D model, the other parameters of the coating are analysed here.

The impacts of the coating property on the generated strain are shown in figure 2. This figure also compares the theoretical results obtained by different models for the strain change caused by 1% RH increase. The relationship between the induced strain and the coating thickness is shown in figure 2(a), the two curves corresponding to the 1D and 3D models almost overlap with each other. Thus, the two models show a very similar impact of the coating thickness on the induced strain. The inset in figure 2(a) shows a small section of the curves to illustrate the minor difference between the two results and to confirm that the 3D model predicts a larger induced strain, as discussed in the previous theoretical analysis.

Non-negligible differences are observed in figures 2(b) and (c): compared with the 3D model, the 1D model seems to underestimate the strain for the same Young's modulus or CHE of the coating. The deviation between the two methods becomes larger as the corresponding parameter increases. This difference should draw the attention of sensor designers. In addition, figures 2(a) and (b) show that the induced strain increases steadily when the coating is thin or soft (low Young's modulus), but the slopes of the curves become smaller on the right hand side of the figure, meaning the influence of the coating thickness and its Young's modulus on the induced strain decreases when the coating is already thick and hard. Equation (4) can provide a straightforward explanation owing to its simple expression. As the thickness or the modulus increases, the influence of coating becomes dominant, and the silica fibre term $A_f E_f$ in the denominator can thus be neglected. As a result, the induced strain turns out to be dependent only on the CHE of the coating. And the strain demonstrates a linear relationship with the coating CHE, as shown by figure 2(c).

Figure 2 has also revealed several ways to enhance the humidity response of the sensing fibre. A thick coating with a high Young's modulus and a large CHE can result in a large strain, which enhances the humidity sensitivity. However, the modulus and CHE are the physical properties of the coating material. The coating thickness can be easily adjusted to improve the sensitivity. It should be noted, however, that thick coating impairs the response time of the sensor [6]. Therefore, the coating should be designed to strike a balance between sensitivity and response time, while also considering the specific application requirements. Fortunately, a response time of approximately 30 min is sufficient for most applications, such as water

ingress monitoring [6]. As a result, the coating can be relatively thick to enhance sensitivity, while the sensing fibre should remain small to minimize its impact on the monitored structure.

2.4. Influence of Poisson's ratio

As presented by equation (6), the Lamé's equations consider the Poisson's ratios of different fibre sections to describe the mechanical changes in three dimensions. This factor has however been totally neglected by the previous studies [4–6, 18, 19], so there is no analysis on its influence of the generated strain. This long-missing subject is investigated in this paper and the result is shown in figure 3. The induced strain is calculated based on the following parameter settings: $r_c = 82.5 \mu\text{m}$, $E_c = 2.5 \text{ GPa}$ and $\alpha_c = 70 \text{ ppm}/\% \text{RH}$.

In the proposed 3D model, the radial deformation of the glass fibre caused by the shape change of the coating is taken into consideration via the Poisson's ratio. Figure 3 shows that the ratios of the coating and the fibre have opposite impacts on the generated strain. After water absorption, the coating expands in both radial and longitudinal directions. The longitudinal expansion plays the main role as it directly stretches the fibre, resulting in the strain ϵ_f . However, the radial expansion might cause a longitudinal compression via the Poisson's ratio η_c , which reduces the longitudinal expansion of the coating. According to the definition of Poisson's ratio, a larger η_c leads to a smaller longitudinal compression, resulting in a larger strain. Meanwhile, the radial change of the coating presses the fibre to make it expand in the longitudinal direction, which contributes to the strain. In this case, a small ratio η_f can lead to a larger longitudinal expansion.

When the Poisson's ratios of the optical fibre and the coating are taken as null, the 3D model neglects the deformation of the fibre and the coating in the radial direction and considers only the mechanical change in the longitudinal direction, therefore, the generated strain shown by equation (11) becomes the same as the result of the 1D model if the CHE of the silica fibre is neglected. As a result, the 1D model is just a simplified case of the 3D model.

3. Experimental conditions

3.1. Sensing fibres

Polyimide is widely used as the coating material because the generated strain shows a linear and reversible relationship with RH [4]. Therefore, this paper focuses on polyimide-coated fibres. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of polyimide are reported as 2.26 GPa and 0.34, respectively [24, 25]. Different CHEs of the polyimide coating have been reported based on the experimentally measured strain, and some reported values are listed in table 1. Note that two coefficients are obtained in [4] as 83 ppm/%RH and 74 ppm/%RH using the 1D model and 3D finite element simulation, respectively, and their average is shown in table 1. The other values are obtained by equation (4). The difference among the reported values may be explained by the curing time and temperature [7, 26]. To reduce the influence of these factors on the theoretical analysis, the CHE is taken here as 74.16 ppm/%RH, the average of the values listed in table 1.

One piece of the standard single mode fibre (SMF) with a typical acrylate coating and three SMFs with different polyimide coatings are used to validate the theoretical analysis. The three polyimide-coated fibres are named F1, F2 and F3. The cladding radius and the coating thickness of F1 and F3 are 62.5 μm and 15 μm , respectively. The main difference between these two fibres is the mode field diameter (MFD), it is 6.4 μm for F1 and 4.2 μm for F3. The fibre F2 has the same MFD as F1, but it is comparatively thin with a 40 μm radius of the cladding and a 11 μm thick coating. The core diameter is slightly smaller than the MFD and can be calculated based on the MFD, numerical aperture and wavelength. In addition, the polyimide coating for fibres F2 and F3 is from a different supplier than that for F1, resulting in distinct coating properties that cause variations in the humidity response. The four different types of SMFs are spliced together in a sequence of the standard SMF, F1, F2 and F3. F3 has a shorter length of ~ 3 m and the other fibres are 3.5 m long.

3.2. Sensing principle of the OFDR system

In order to characterize the four fibres simultaneously, distributed fibre sensing must be used. A commercial OFDR is employed here because of its high spatial resolution and high sensitivity. Although this section focuses on the experimental conditions, the working principle of the sensing system is briefly introduced here to facilitate understanding for those unfamiliar with this technique. A highly coherent laser is used in the system as the light source, and its wavelength is linearly scanned during the measurement. The continuous light from the laser is at first split; one part is used as a probe and launched into the sensing fibre, and the other serves as a local oscillator (LO). The probe light gets scattered during its travelling through the fibre. A small portion of the scattered light travels backwards and mixes with the LO for photodetection. Due to the time-of-flight of the light and the wavelength scanning light source, the backscattered light and the LO have different optical frequencies, and this difference changes with the fibre position. Therefore, it is possible to retrieve the distance information from the beat frequency between the backscattered light and the LO. Thus, a temporal trace can be obtained along the fibre.

The OFDR system relies on the reflection spectrum shift of the backscattered light to quantify environmental variation. Usually, the reflection spectrum at a given position is constructed by the Fourier transform of the obtained temporal trace around that position. The spectrum shifts once the environmental condition changes [29] and spectral shift $\Delta\nu$ has a linear relationship with the strain change $\Delta\varepsilon$ as [30]

$$\Delta\nu = -\nu \left\{ 1 - n^2/2 \cdot [P_{12} - \eta_f(P_{11} + P_{12})] \right\} \Delta\varepsilon, \quad (13)$$

where ν represents the optical frequency of the incident light, η_f is the Poisson's ratio of the silica fibre, $n = 1.456$ is the refractive index of the fibre, $P_{11} = 0.121$ and $P_{12} \approx 0.27$ are Pockels coefficients [31]. The OFDR works around 1550 nm ($\nu = 193.5$ THz), thus the corresponding strain sensitivity ($\Delta\nu/\Delta\varepsilon$) is -149 MHz/ $\mu\varepsilon$. Using this coefficient, the sensor directly provides the strain information. Because the OFDR system shares the same working principle as a standard fibre Bragg grating (FBG), they should demonstrate the same strain sensitivity. A similar strain sensitivity of 1.201 pm/ $\mu\varepsilon = -149.86$ MHz/ $\mu\varepsilon$ has been reported for a polyimide coated FBG [32], validating that the theoretically derived sensitivity can be applied to convert the experimentally measured spectral shift into strain. Note that the OFDR system can also measure temperature because the spectral shift $\Delta\nu$ has a linear relationship with temperature change [29].

The OFDR measurement is repeated every 5 min for the humidity response characterisation of the different fibres. The wavelength scans from 1525.5 nm to 1610.8 nm, reaching a high spatial resolution of

Table 1. Reported coefficient of humidity expansion of polyimide coating.

CHE ppm/%RH	78.5	90	58	70	74.3
References	[4]	[5]	[7]	[27]	[28]

Figure 5. Measured temperature and relative humidity inside the climate chamber during the measurement.

10 μm . The reflection spectrum is constructed from every 10 mm long section of the temporal trace with a sensor spacing of 2 mm. In this way, the frequency shift of the spectrum is obtained along the sensing fibre.

3.3. Testing conditions

In order to characterise the humidity responses of the four fibres and explore their temperature dependence, the fibres are loosely coiled into spools and experience humidity changes in a climate chamber (KK-105 CHLT from Kambič) at a given temperature. The entire characterization setup is shown in figure 4, different fibre spools are placed in the climate chamber and an OFDR system is employed to perform the measurement. The RH is increased from 10% to 90% with a 20% step and each step lasts 2 h for the stabilisation and the measurement. The humidity response is characterised at 40 °C, 60 °C, 80 °C and 90 °C to investigate its temperature dependence.

The built-in sensors are used to record the temperature and RH inside the climate chamber every 5 s during the measurement, and the results are shown in figure 5. Spikes are visible at the beginning of every temperature or humidity change, as indicated in the shaded region. In these regions the internal environment fails to reach the set condition, causing unreliable results, thus the measurements within these time intervals are discarded. Additionally, the RH sometimes becomes unstable, e.g. 70%RH at 80 °C and 90 °C. The frequency shift measured under such conditions is averaged to suppress the influence of the humidity random variation.

4. Experimental results and discussion

The OFDR measurement is performed repeatedly, and the frequency shift is calculated along the whole sensing fibre with the four different types. The result is plotted in figure 5 over the entire measurement time and sensing distance. The frequency shifts obtained at various fibre sections change stepwise as a function of the measurement time due to the internal environmental change of the climate chamber. Figure 6 shows clearly that the sensing fibre consists of four fibre sections with the boundaries at ~ 6.9 m, ~ 10.5 m and ~ 14 m as their humidity responses are different. The first fibre section is the standard SMF with the acrylate coating. Only a few shift changes are visible, which are induced by the temperature variation. More changes

Figure 6. Frequency shift measured by the OFDR system over the entire measurement time along the sensing fibre.

Figure 7. Humidity responses of the four different types of fibres at temperature of (a) 40 °C, (b) 60 °C, (c) 80 °C, and (d) 90 °C.

can be seen for the fibre sections with the polyimide coating, because their humidity response is higher due to the responsive coating material. The four different types of optical fibres are spliced together, and the splice points are protected by heat shrink tubes. These tubes have a different response to temperature and humidity, therefore the frequency shift measured at the splicing positions between the fibre sections is much larger. Consequently, they are excluded from the calculation of the humidity sensitivity.

The theoretical analysis reveals that the humidity induced strain is dependent on several physical properties of the fibre coating. It is very challenging and even impossible to fabricate the coating with perfectly uniform properties along the fibre. For example, the tolerance of the coating thickness is $\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$ for F1 and F3 according to the manufacturer. Such a variation causes inevitably a nonuniform response along the fibre. The frequency shift is averaged over each fibre section to minimise the impact of this coating nonuniformity. Furthermore, the shift is averaged over time under each temperature and humidity condition in order to minimise the environmental fluctuations, particularly the small temperature variation, inside the climate chamber, as explained in the last section. In this way the obtained result is more reliable.

After averaging over distance and time, the obtained frequency shift becomes a point for each fibre type under a given temperature and humidity condition. At each temperature, the average shift obtained at 10% RH (30% for 40 °C) is subtracted from all the shifts obtained under this temperature condition, and the results are shown in figure 7. It is obvious that the shift changes linearly with the RH for all types of fibres, and the corresponding humidity sensitivity can be determined from the slope of these lines. As expected, the standard SMF exhibits the least sensitivity to humidity, agreeing with the reported result [6], because the acrylate coating is much less responsive to humidity than the polyimide material [33]. The standard acrylate coating for telecom fibres usually has two layers, the outer layer protects the fibre from physical damage and the inner one is used to minimise the bending loss [34]. The inner layer is very soft and hinders the strain transfer to the silica fibre [23], resulting in a low humidity sensitivity.

Figure 8. The humidity sensitivities of the four different types of fibres at different temperatures.

The three fibres with polyimide coatings exhibit various humidity responses owing to their property difference in the silica fibre and the coating. The orange line is always above the others, indicating the fibre F1 has the largest humidity sensitivity. At 40 °C, the humidity sensitivities of F1, F2 and F3 are -199.9 MHz/%RH, -169.6 MHz/%RH and -104.4 MHz/%RH, respectively. The fibres F2 and F3 are clearly less sensitive than the F1 fibre probably due to the difference in the coating property. It is interesting to note that the fibre F2 is more sensitive than the F3 even though it has a thinner coating. This is because of the small size of that fibre, whose cross-section area is just $\sim 40\%$ of the fibre F3. Thereby, the fibre term $A_f E_f$ in the denominator of equation (4) becomes much smaller, leading to a larger humidity-induced strain.

Based on the fibre property listed in sections 2.3 and 3.1, the strain change in the silica fibre caused by 1% RH increase can be calculated using 1D and 3D models. According to the strain sensitivity of -149 MHz/ $\mu\epsilon$, the calculated strain is converted into the humidity sensitivity for the comparison with the experimental result. The 3D model estimates the sensitivity of the fibre F1 as -219.5 MHz/%RH, and it becomes -183.4 MHz/%RH according to the 1D model. However, the theoretical models are unable to estimate the sensitivity of F2 and F3 due to insufficient information about their coatings.

The theoretical result is close to the experimentally obtained sensitivity of fibre F1 at 40 °C, with errors of 9.8% and -8.2% for 3D and 1D models, respectively. The discrepancy between the theoretical estimation and the experimental result is probably due to the inaccurate information used for the calculation. The coating properties vary from different manufacturers as they use different fabrication processes. For example, the CHE of the polyimide coating is dependent on the curing temperature and time [5, 26]. The Young's modulus is also supposed to depend on the fabrication condition. In addition, the polyimide properties are related to the chemical structure, functional groups and molecular weight [34]. Reported parameters are used for the theoretical analysis instead of the actual information of the fibre F1, resulting in the discrepancy. Moreover, all the reported CHEs are obtained based on the 1D model, so this method has a smaller error than the 3D model. It is therefore important to acquire accurate information about the coating property in order to make a reliable estimation of the humidity response.

The humidity sensitivity of different fibres at different temperatures is summarised in figure 8. The sensitivity of the standard SMF decreases from 40 °C to 80 °C, agreeing with the reported result [35]. The sensitivity becomes larger at 90 °C probably due to the coating property change, as the acrylate coating has a low working temperature up to 85 °C [34]. The fibres with polyimide coatings also become less responsive to the humidity change at high temperatures. This is probably due to the coating property change at high temperatures. A few studies have experimentally demonstrated that the Young's modulus of the polyimide decreases as the temperature increases [21, 36]. In addition, other coating properties like the CHE and Poisson's ratio may change with temperature, degrading the humidity sensitivity. Another point is the strain response change at different temperatures. Due to the thermo-optic effect, the refractive index of the fibre increases at high temperature, so the strain sensitivity reduces according to equation (13). It has been experimentally demonstrated that the strain sensitivity of FBG decreases almost linearly as the temperature increases [37]. All these issues lead to the reduced humidity sensitivity at high temperatures. The experimental result provides solid proof that the humidity response of the polyimide coated fibre is temperature dependent, so it is necessary to calibrate the response under different thermal conditions to deliver reliable humidity measurement.

It is important to note that humidity sensing based on strain measurement often faces cross-sensitivity with temperature, as most fibre optic strain sensors are also sensitive to temperature changes. Therefore, both humidity and temperature must be measured simultaneously to eliminate the influence of

temperature-induced changes. Fortunately, existing techniques for discriminating between strain and temperature, such as employing two sensing systems [38] or using two fibres with distinct responses [32], can be directly applied to this issue. Moreover, machine learning has proven to be an effective approach for simultaneous humidity and temperature sensing [20].

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the humidity sensitivity of the optical fibre with a hygroscopic coating is comprehensively investigated, and its thermal dependence is experimentally revealed. This study analyses the strain transfer from the coating to the silica fibre using 1D and 3D models, and the analytical expression of the humidity induced strain is derived. Both models show that the humidity response relies mostly on the coating properties, which may change with temperature. The humidity sensitivity of different polyimide coated fibres are experimentally determined and turns out to decrease as the temperature increases. The theoretical analysis agrees well with the experimental result and the temperature dependence of the humidity sensitivity is analysed. The theoretical model can offer more reliable guidance for humidity sensor design, and the experimental result shows the necessity to calibrate the humidity response under different thermal conditions in real applications.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researchers. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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